

INTERDEPENDENCE OF PRODUCTION AND CONSUMPTION

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Annotation: *In this article, the role of domestically produced products and services, their interdependence with consumption, as well as their importance to each other, if one does not work, the other will have a significant impact on the process of processing. we see In order to timely replenish the consumer goods in the consumer basket, it is necessary to produce products, and for this purpose to allocate space for new products and services that need to be created in a timely manner in the goods and services created by the population. will be necessary, the article will explore the above-mentioned organic linkage, production process, purchasing power and population consumption in more detail.*

Keywords: *Budget, Commodity, consumption, GDP, income.*

The consumer and the enterprise are the main agents of market relations. they create supply and demand in the market, take an active part in determining the equilibrium price. in this case, the modern economy appeals to the consumer as the highest link of the market economy because it, with its own money, votes "yes" or "no" to the goods produced by the producer. Today, in developed countries, consumer spending accounts for three-quarters of GDP. This suggests that consumer behavior is the most important factor in economic development.

Typically, consumer behavior is explained by:

A useful, sensible line is to take action, that is, to increase the narcissism that one sees in one's income.

We can assume that the consumer will have a clear idea of the goods and services offered in the average consumer market in distinguishing product preferences. We assume that buyers have a clear idea of how they will ultimately benefit from each subsequent unit product they can purchase.

Limitations in the budget (family income).

Prices. The production of goods requires the use of economic resources, and therefore they have a certain price. A limited-income buyer buys a limited amount of goods. Therefore, it is necessary to choose from the alternative products the ones that best meet their needs.

Consumer behavior is viewed in terms of marginal utility and indifference curves.

Marginal utility is the increase in the total utility of a commodity in the growth of consumption per unit. At the same time, as the amount of commodity consumed increases, the marginal utility of each additional commodity unit decreases.

As far as possible, the consumer seeks to purchase a group of goods for his limited income in order to allow him to meet his needs to the maximum.

Each indifference curve graphically represents different sets of products that have the same navf for the consumer.

Indifference curve

Since the same level of utility is ensured at all points on the indifference curve, the decrease in gross utility due to the increase in consumption of product F must balance the decrease in consumption of product C.

More or less demand for products depends on the financial capacity of the family (household), ie the family budget. A family budget or family opportunity is the amount of money that can be used to buy the highest amount of products, if the family income decreases, then the curve decreases, if the family budget increases without changing the price of goods, the budget curve also decreases and vice versa.

If the price of products and consumer income increase or decrease at the same time, the budget curve will not change.

while the budget curve shows what each family can afford, the indifference curve shows what each family wants to get.

If we assume that there are two types of goods F (food) and S (clothing head) and assume that the income of the buyer who buys it is \$ 40; if a unit of food is worth one dollar, a garment is worth \$ 2, and all proceeds of \$ 40 are spent on the purchase of clothing, then the buyer can purchase a maximum of 20 units of type A goods. This can be seen from the table and graph data below. The set of goods in options B, C and D shows the potential to spend \$ 40.

Brand selection and budget line

Package (options)	Food (F)	Clothin g(S)	Total expenses (dollars)
A	0	20	40
B	10	15	40
C	20	10	40
D	30	5	40
E	40	0	40

By summarizing the data in the table, you can create a graphical budget line.

If the family's demand is met by the desired proportion of goods, then the family's demand for such goods is negligible.

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